

Event Abstract

Libyan Medical Education: The National Accreditation and WFME Criteria

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The advancement of developing countries can be refereed to according on how they merge the field of education into everyday life, and how this influences the healthcare system. The international increasing demand on healthcare has affected medical education, and this led to various trends including pronounced upsurge in the number of medical schools and students, causing migration for medical education and training. This marked growth in medical education system bring about a concern regarding the quality assurance of individual graduates and their educational programs.

The recent global progressions and changes in medical education will create a great burden on the third world countries, including Libya. Fourteen years after the NCQAA was first established, its mission now to assist and guide medical schools in Libya for the World Federation for Medical Education (WFME) accreditation standards. WFME was initiated on the initiative of the WHO and the World Medical Association (WMA) with the mission of evaluating agencies that accredit basic medical education. In 2004, WHO and the WFME established the global task force on accreditation in medical education.

Although it gives the impression that unlikely Libyan medical collages will have a WFME-recognized accrediting authority by 2023, medical schools in Libya is encouraged to be accredited by the national accreditation center to be involved in the WMFE accreditation program. The increasing worldwide number of institutions that applying for global recognition, and have almost completed the recognition process, should increase our local authorities' enthusiasm to recommends our medical schools for prompt accreditation. Thus, there must be some mechanism of formal peer review process of

medical schools is likely to benefit our local medical education.

It becomes an obligatory role for all sectors of Libyan medical education to strive to introduce the accreditation standers to all medical schools in our country. Hence, the opportunity of attaining a suitable education system will be easy and a reachable goal. Moreover, NCQAA is advised to consider the new international transformation of the education system and go through the process of revising standards of accreditation and standardizing the process to meet the global task force on accreditation in medical education. We hope that our rigorous efforts can endure to advance the quality of medical education in Libya.

Keywords: WFME, Criteria, Accreditation, Education

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